

application. Dissipation was 94.4% (0.05% and 0.1%) 20 d after application.

Rate of degradation with both applications seemed to follow the first-order reaction (see figure).

Fifty percent of the toxicant was reduced at 1.4 d and 1.95 d and the safe waiting period (T_{50}) was 15.9 d and 17.5 d for lower and higher applications.

Grain and straw samples had nondetectable levels of quinalphos. □

Effect of plant age on rice susceptibility to yellow stem borer (YSB) *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Walker)

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YSB, the most important of the 21 species of stem borers that attack rice, is widespread in tropical Asia and Japan. All rice crops, whether irrigated, lowland rainfed, upland, or deepwater, suffer damage. Adults oviposit on leaves and newly emerged larvae enter stems and feed on the inner walls, causing deadhearts at the vegetative stage and whiteheads at the reproductive stage.

We studied larval survival and degree of damage on rice plants of different ages. Seeding of IR64 was staggered so plants of different ages were available for simultaneous infestation with first-instar larvae. There were 12 pots/age group. Plants were thinned to 20 tillers/pot. Each pot was infested with 15 larvae hatched from field-collected egg masses and then covered with a 40 × 100-cm mylar film cage.

Four pots were dissected at 18 d and 4 pots at 25 d after infestation (DAI). Adults were allowed to emerge on four pots.

Larvae recovered by dissecting plants at 18 DAI were weighed individually. Individuals recovered from plants at 25 DAI could not be weighed as some had reached the prepupal stage. The remaining plants were cut about 20 cm above the soil for easy observation of emerging adults.

Survival and development of *S. incertulas* larvae and damage at different days after infestation (DAI) on IR64 plants of different ages.^a IIRRI, 1987.

Plant age (DAS)	Larval wt (mg/larva) 18 DAI	Survival (%)		Adults emerged (no.)	Deadhearts (%)	
		18 DAI	25 DAI		18 DAI	25 DAI
10	0 e	0 d	1 d	0 d	10 c	9 e
16	7.8 d	2 cd	2 cd	0 d	22 b	12 d
22	8.9 d	2 cd	4 cd	0 d	25 b	14 d
28	12.8 c	4 c	5 c	5 c	27 b	16 cd
34	34.1 ab	68 a	55 a	33 b	69 a	66 ab
40	41.2 a	68 a	52 a	63 a	69 a	11 a
46	33.3 ab	37 b	49 a	48 b	57 a	56 b
52	29.8 b	28 b	28 b	41 b	27 b	26 c

^aAv of 4 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

Fewer larvae survived and emerged on younger rice plants (see table). Survival increased with plant age up to 34 and 40 d after sowing (DAS), then declined progressively on plants aged 46 and 52 DAS. Fewer deadhearts were

observed in younger plants than in plants at 34, 40, and 46 DAS; deadheart count declined sharply at 52 DAS.

Larvae were heaviest on plants at 40 DAS; they weighed less on plants at 34, 46, and 52 DAS. □

Fecundity of several green leaf hopper (GLH) populations in Indonesia

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A greenhouse experiment Jan-Apr 1985 was designed to study the fecundity of GLH *Nephotettix virescens* Distant

populations from four sites in Indonesia: Salutete and Pangkajene (South Sulawesi), Tawamalewe (South East Sulawesi), and Citamiang (West Java).

A pair of mature GLH was placed in a test tube containing a 2-wk-old TNI seedling. Number of eggs laid was counted daily under the microscope. Fecundity differed in the four locations (see table). □

Fecundity of *N. virescens* Distant from four Indonesian populations^a, 1985.

Origin of population	Pre-oviposition period (d)	Oviposition period (d)	Postoviposition period (d)	Eggs (no.)
Salutete	6 a	23 a	2 a	260 a
Pangkajene	8 a	11 b	2 a	81 c
Tawamalewe	7 a	18 ab	2 a	151 bc
Citamiang	6 a	22 a	1 a	213 ab

^aIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Effect of sweep-net sampling at rice crop reproductive stage on yield

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Orthopteran predators such as *Metioche vittaticollis*, *Anaxipha longipennis*, and

Conocephalus longipennis, as well as certain pests such as rice bugs and green leafhoppers often are abundant in fields where rice plants are at the reproductive stage. Sweep-net sampling, an efficient method of collecting these highly mobile insects in the field, might damage the flowering plants and affect yields. Yet it is important to sample insects to make

appropriate management decisions.

We set up a trial to determine possible effects of sweep-net sampling on rice yields. IR62, IR64, and IR1917-3-17 were transplanted 20 d after seeding at 25 × 25 cm. Each field was divided into 24 6.25- × 8.3-m plots. Four treatments were replicated six times in a randomized complete block design.

We sampled weekly for 3 consecutive weeks starting at 67 d after transplanting (DT), making 1, 3, or 6 passes through a

Effect on yield of sweep-net sampling for 3 consecutive weeks beginning 67 DT. IRRI, 1987.

Passes through the plot (no.)	Yield ^a (t/ha)		
	IR62	IR64	IR1917-3-17
0	3.7 a	3.8 a	3.2 a
1	3.2 ab	3.6 a	3.2 a
3	3.2 ab	3.7 a	3.0 b
6	3.0 b	3.6 a	2.8 b

^a Av of 6 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 10% level by DMRT.

plot. The sampler made 10 sweeps/pass.

There was no significant difference in yields of IR64 from the different sweep-net pass patterns (see table). However, sterile spikelets at harvest should be evaluated. From 0 to three passes through IR62 did not significantly affect yields, but 6 passes did. Yield of IR1917-3-17 decreased with 3-6 passes. One pass through the field did not significantly affect yield of any variety. □

Leaffolder (LF) outbreak in Haryana

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LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* (Guenée) has been observed in most rice-growing areas of Haryana, but its incidence has been below the economic threshold. Our regular pest monitoring surveys now show that since 1983, LF has started to cause significant damage to the rice crop. A severe outbreak was observed during 1987 kharif (Jul to mid-Oct).

We surveyed extensively during 1987 to monitor LF in the major crop areas—Kurukshehra, Karnal, Ambala, Jind, Sirsa, and Sonapat. Peak incidence was in mid-September when rice was at the panicle emergence stage. In 13 of 145 villages surveyed, 1-5% leaves were found damaged; in 28 villages, 5-25%; in 44 villages, 50%; and in 60 villages, more than 50%. Populations ranged from 2 to 20 larvae/hill. PR106 and Basmati 370 were the most affected rice varieties.

The nitrogenous fertilizer recommendation for these ricefields is 100-140 kg N/ha. Excessive application of nitrogenous fertilizer, coupled with indiscriminate application of granular pesticides and other formulations, could have resulted in resurgence.

Average monsoon rainfall is 500-750 mm during kharif. But in 1987 kharif, unprecedented drought Jul-Oct could have affected the insect population. □

Acoustic signal-producing organ of brown planthopper (BPH)

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Prior to copulation, both male and female adults of the rice BPH communicate primarily by means of

acoustic signals emitted by specialized signal-producing organs. We investigated the structure and function of those organs.

The signal-producing organ (possessed only by the adults) is situated on both sides of the juncture of the pterothorax and abdomen (Fig. 1). It is composed of a sclerotizing coxata and a petal-like sclerite extended in the front of the third sternopleuron (the first and second sternopleuron are underdeveloped and invisible). The underside

1. I. Acoustic signal producing organ of *N. lugens* in lateral view. II. Coxata in posterior view. III. Petal-like sclerite in the front of third sternopleuron in anterior view, arrow points upward. IV. Flaky processes on the top of coxata. A = petal-like sclerite, B = coxata, C = a hole before coxata, D = the top of coxata covered with flaky processes, E = pterothorax, F = trochantin, G = femur, H = underside of the sclerite.